

Social media's "Twitter" & "Instagram" influence on crimes and how that
could be prevented

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates how the social media platforms "Twitter" & "Instagram" influence crimes and how these platforms create incentives for violence. Typically, social media platforms are used for recreational and entertainment purposes. However, several studies have shown how social media platforms influence deviant behavior. Both directly and indirectly, social media platforms play a role in shaping today's criminal activity. This research aims to locate the targeted group/audience influenced by crimes shown on Twitter & Instagram, define authority in the 21st century and who has the authority to influence, why & how this is a problem, why we should be concerned, and what this means for the future generations.

This research will also address how much more Twitter & Instagram can influence users, increasing deviant behavior ten years from now, based on the growth pattern over the past ten years. The repercussions of the issue, what might happen if we do not limit social media's influence and regulate the platforms? What methods worked in regulating Twitter & Instagram's authority and what did/will not? How these platforms created new avenues or paths to crime perpetration, and how Twitter and Instagram made victimization visible.

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Summary

Both or either Instagram and Twitter play significant roles in shaping the characters of almost every juvenile. Whether it is the need to keep up with society or the urge to jump on the latest trend, juveniles almost always feel pressured by these tech giants. The detrimental influence on juveniles grows as users become more attached to these and other platforms. "Social media has become recognized as a vehicle through which youth perpetuate acts of violence against their peers, such as bullying, harassment, dating aggression, and gang-related crimes. In addition, social media has also been used as a vehicle for inflicting self-harm—most notably, cyber-suicide." (Cash, Thelwall, Peck, Ferrell, & Bridge, 2013; Hinduja & Patchin, 2010; Ruder, Hatch, Ampanozi, Thali, & Fischer, 2011).

Twitter & Instagram's effects on users can be positive or negative depending solely on the post, tweet, or message being shared, making these platforms dangerous to all extents. When it narrows down to user safety, these platforms have shown disinterest. Twitter & Instagram are invested in the usage of their media more than their users' safety, allowing users to view violent posts regardless of the warning signs these platforms attach. A derivative organization that has no benefit in social media businesses is required to interfere with banning the spread of successful and planned attacks.

1.2 Objective of the Research

This research aims to analyze how the social media platforms "Twitter" & "Instagram" influence crimes, how these platforms created incentives for violence, and how we can prevent

further influences. Typically, social media platforms are used for recreational purposes. However, several studies have shown how social media platforms influence deviant behavior, "youth violence—whether bullying, gang violence, or self-directed violence—increasingly occurs in the online space." (Patton, Hong, Ranney, Patel, Kelley, Eschmann, & Washington, 2014). Both directly and indirectly, social media platforms play a role in shaping today's criminal activity. This research aims to locate the targeted audience, influenced by crimes shown on Twitter & Instagram, define authority in the 21st-century meaning, who can influence behaviors today, why/how this is a problem, why we should be concerned, and what this is means for future generations.

Some of the findings in this research from (Cash, Thelwall, Peck, Ferrell, & Bridge, 2013; Hinduja & Patchin, 2010; Ruder, Hatch, Ampanozi, Thali, & Fischer, 2011) show how Twitter & Instagram under social media's impression can influence youth. This research will also present the repercussions of the issue, what will happen if we do not regulate these platforms, what methods worked in regulating Twitter & Instagram's authority and what did not, how these platforms created new avenues to crime perpetration, how Twitter and Instagram made victimization visible, and recent crimes that social media platforms have introduced.

CHAPTER 2: RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Five research questions have been proposed in this paper. The questions are divided into seven sections by order of what issue resulted in the appearance of the other. The first section highlights this paper's main concern or core argument, "Twitter" & "Instagram's" authority. The question is proposed as "who has authority to influence." The second section deals with the impact of excessive authority social media platforms have on users. The third section aims to locate the victims/targeted group.

The fourth and fifth sections investigate how these platforms influence deviant behavior through crime perpetration and victimization visibility. The sixth section dives into the repercussions of influence and what problems have been created/introduced. The final section deals with the outcomes/results from influence and how this could evolve soon. This section also introduces ways to regulate Twitter and Instagram's authorities and what methods to control these platforms and did not. The questions proposed in this research are:

- A. Who has the authority to influence juvenile deviant behavior in the 21st century, and the outcomes of this influence?
- B. How do "Twitter" & "Instagram" influence crimes, and how did these platforms create incentives for violence?
- C. Who are the targeted audience influenced by crimes portrayed on these platforms?
- D. How Twitter & Instagram created new avenues to crime perpetration, and how was victimization made visible on these platforms?
- E. What are the repercussions of the issue, what methods worked in regulating Twitter & Instagram's authority, and what did not?

CHAPTER 3: LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 Authority: Who has authority to influence in the 21st century

Twitter & Instagram's influence can emanate from leaders, celebrities, opinion shapers, governments, or organizations with many followers. The availability, convenience, and affordability of online platforms give anyone the authority to sway opinions and perceptions of followers in social networks. Tweets are gaining more popularity and having more influence on users, as Twitter users are increasing. "Since its emergence in mid-2006, Twitter's user base has continued to grow. Statistics Canada (2013) data revealed that 67% of Internet users in Canada used social networking sites between 2010 and 2012. A more recent survey found that 42% of Canadians with an online presence have a Twitter account specifically, with the greatest use being among youth ages 18 to 24 (Gruzd, Jacobson, Mai, & Dubois, 2018)." (Peters, Costello, & Crane, 2).

An influencer's effect on a user's decision-making and behavior may be positive or negative. However, that depends solely on the influencer's intention when posting, tweeting, or delivering their message, making it dangerous to all extents. For instance, political leaders can disseminate false information to achieve their propagandist plan to win votes. Scenarios of fake details and propaganda have necessitated some countries, such as France, to enact laws that prevent the spread of misleading or inaccurate allegations by political leaders during campaigns. Thus, other individuals can still influence opinions on social media platforms.

3.2 Influence: How "Twitter" & "Instagram" influence crimes and how they created incentives for violence.

Social media revolutionized how humans interact with one another. The benefits have allowed friends and family members to maintain contact over the years while planning events and sharing memories from any part of the world. Nonetheless, the platform has allowed cybercriminals to engage in harassment, cyberbullying, and other technologies that have contributed to the toxic nature of social media. The advent of social media has affected how malicious individuals commit crimes (Lowry et al., 2016). Crimes that may arise from too much influence from Twitter or Instagram include hate crimes, cyberbullying, online fraud, etc. Trending hashtags leave opposite implications of severe crime. Despite the severity of the crime, the rewards might excel the likelihood of being caught or punished, making criminal activities more visible.

While law enforcement is embracing social media to stop or investigate crime, there is no denying that these new forms of interaction have contributed to criminal activity. The most significant incentive created by social media to commit crime comes from the anonymity that it promotes. Accountability requires the identification of the individual responsible for any misconduct. However, when most people open a web browser or an app, they expect relative obscurity, detached from their physical identity. Child pornography is one example that requires too much user anonymity. While hiding their identities, criminals can perform crimes with impunity certainty.

"Anonymity can be used to protect a criminal performing many different crimes, for example, slander, distribution of child pornography, illegal threats, racial agitation, fraud,

intentional damage such as distribution of computer viruses, etc." (Palme, 4). While law enforcement agencies might have an easier time tracking criminals if all online activity was strictly tied to one's identity, most people would not make that trade. The fact that profit-maximizing companies own all popular social media platforms explains why the public is unwilling to surrender total privacy online.

The desire to separate one's online identity from their physical life allows social media to be used for criminal activities. Criminals can easily exploit people's digital profiles for cyberbullying and doxing without worrying about getting caught, especially if they take steps to cover their digital footprint from authorities (Malleon & Andresen. 2015). Anonymity also creates an environment that encourages would-be criminals to go through with their intentions. These individuals would be hesitant to commit the crime in real life. The abstraction that an online identity or its lack thereof encourages people to engage in malicious behavior.

3.3 Target: Audience influenced by crimes portrayed on "Twitter" & "Instagram."

Twitter & Instagram have been trending discussion topics since their release. 2006 revolutionized how people could share their thoughts and have a loud voice without speaking a word. Users saw this revolution as more freedom of expression, politicians saw it as votes, and leaders saw it as followers, believing that retweets meant public consensus. Twitter gave many what they have been searching for, a loud, heard, and, more importantly, ungoverned voice. However, that is not all that Twitter delivered. To acknowledge the benefits of anything, one must consider the detriments.

Twitter & Instagram exposed users to crimes more than before, like other social media

platforms. In the past, one had to be present at a scene or watch crime news on T.V. Even though crimes might have been reported on T.V. regularly, it was slower than what is presented on Twitter & Instagram's hashtags. These hashtags, however, are accessible by everyone. Adolescents have access to crimes and what follows by simply creating an account. Even though users must enter their age when creating an account, anyone could manipulate and register as an adult. Because Twitter & Instagram do not require further identifications, adolescents are exposed to the identical posts and tweets visible to adults.

Propagation of harmful content shapes public opinions and social decisions, some of the shared posts and tweets, such as violent or terrorist videos, lead to anarchy and lawlessness. Crime content is easily shared, and misinformation is spread faster on social media platforms than mainstream media due to peer effect, lack of appropriate regulation, anonymity, and freedom of speech. When it comes to the targeted audience, juveniles remain the primary concern to many.

3.4 Avenues: New paths to crime perpetration learned from Twitter & Instagram

Twitter and Instagram provided an avenue for criminals to track targeted victims. People met and interacted with on social platforms while sharing pictures and information about their favorite spots, where they reside, and their current location. Such personal information made individuals an easy target because criminals can trace any potential victim. Furthermore, new forms of crime, including revenge pornography, were committed on Instagram. As a result, the two networking platforms facilitated criminals in perpetrating illegal activities and led to new unlawful behaviors. Most of the activities are incentivized, increasing deviant behavior on these

platforms, and motivating other users to become a part of illegal activities.

It is important to note that some of the crimes social media encourages are different from what was traditionally considered criminal behavior. Social media has made it easier to undertake crimes that were historically difficult to execute. These include money laundering, distributing objectionable material, child pornography, fraud, hacking, terrorism, and drug dealing (Malleon & Andresen. 2015). Each of these vices existed before the commercialization of the web infrastructure. However, they were relatively difficult to commit since they needed the perpetrator to interact physically with their victim or crime partners, creating an avenue for law enforcement to lay a trap.

In addition, the scale to which criminals could commit acts such as distributing illegal material or dumping confidential information was much smaller. With anonymity, they can efficiently distribute illegal content or personal data in minutes to billions of people worldwide without getting caught. Today, international cybercriminals have formed cartels that strike their targets every few months or years. In general, social media and the web have provided a buffer that ensures their operations from several countries without leaving a trace.

In addition, technologies such as the Tor and VPN networks allow criminals to bounce their network activity across the world, making it impossible to pinpoint the source of an attack (Krunoslav et al.. 2018). Most VPN providers use privacy as their key selling point. Companies such as Proton and Windscribe do not log the network activities of their users. Law enforcement agencies would have little use for the metadata stored in their servers since it is encrypted.

Traditionally, cybercriminals were often apprehended at the point of extracting money from their subjects. With blockchain technology that powers the anonymous digital currency

exchange, this window is shutting (Demirkan et al., 2020). Some cryptocurrencies guarantee total privacy from law enforcement. The shift to NFTs or non-fungible tokens as a store of online value means that the need for physical money will continue to dwindle. Criminals will no longer have to worry about converting their online loot into currency. They will use anonymously sourced digital currencies to handle real-life transactions.

In addition, there is a general shift in the public's discourse from communication platforms that monitor networks to encrypted alternatives such as Signal and Telegram. When summoned, these services do not maintain network logs and cannot submit any metadata to law enforcement. It means that messages exchanged between a criminal and a subject disappear forever once deleted. As more people embrace privacy, social media, anonymous communication, and digital value exchange, online crimes will continue to rise.

An organized crime on social media looks like this, using VPN to ensure user anonymity, then using Instagram & Twitter to locate the target. Once the target is found, they are influenced or trapped in becoming the crime victim. Other apps such as Telegram are used as accessories to ensure the crime's completion without leaving traces. Finally, digital currencies or cryptocurrencies are relied on if the crime committed is incentivized.

3.5 Visibility: How Twitter & Instagram made victimization visible

Twitter and Instagram do not ban perceived violent content on their platforms in response to freedom of expression and speech. It is easier to regulate traditional media and content because of the existing frameworks. However, the media's landscape has significantly changed over the years since content sharing and consumption is no longer constrained by boundaries

and professionalism (Brainard, 2018). With online platforms, anyone from any part of the globe can create and share content with an international audience in real-time. Differentiating between freedom of speech and criminal law is challenging under the current framework. The changing culture and dynamics of the use of social media have changed. The situation makes it difficult for Twitter and Instagram to prohibit what is posted beforehand.

The two platforms made victimization visible by showing how the public treats the suspected offenders. Online anonymity encourages users to victimize individuals that have been targeted for harassment (Chan et al., 2020). It is common for web users to blame victims of cybercrime that have weak passwords, share too much, create posts, or engage with people who turned out to be criminals. Like cybercriminals, ordinary social media users find it easy to harass and victimize people that have suffered at the hands of malicious people due to anonymity. It is important to note that having a profile picture and a genuine identity on social media reduces the probability of online hatred. However, the fact that one needs to find the time to open social media apps and locate a conversation creates that feeling that the online avatar is a separate identity.

Instagram and Twitter have been linked with the rising rates of cyber victimization. On Instagram, users have reported cyber victimization as one gains popularity. The problem increases as people demand online validation, affecting their psychological well-being when attention is negative. Studies show that people who spend more time on social media face more cyber victimization than their counterparts (Longobardi et al., 2020). Online victimization has real-world impacts on individuals, such as sleeping problems, suicidal thoughts, symptoms of post-traumatic stress, or depression.

3.6 Repercussions: Why this is a problem & why we should be concerned

Social media platforms display crimes because, in a free or liberal world, individuals have the right to express themselves without being censored. People can freely share their opinions and feelings or aspects that define individuals in the current era. According to Brainard (2018), the perpetrators use social media to engage with their viewers by promoting their actions, winning the publics' acceptance, and validating their attitudes under the circumstances preceding the activity. This "freedom" allows people to share hate speeches on their network without fear of being reprimanded by the law or regulations of social media platforms.

Twitter and Instagram allowing crimes to be posted on their platforms are problematic because it increases crime cases, at least online. They allow crimes to be published either by not banning the user from posting in the future or not restricting criminal posts. Twitter and Instagram restrict these posts by showing warning signs before the post, which could be dismissed, limiting the warning's effectiveness.

Research indicates that the consumption of crime news on social networking platforms increases the fear and probability of people engaging in illegal activities (Nisi et al., 2021). People fear violence when they consume news that influences public perceptions of crime. The prevalence of anxiety for being victims of street violence is high among youths and women. Accordingly, a large portion of the population tends to develop avoidance behavior to cope with the situation. The public perceives an upsurge of unlawful activities as a significant threat to crime news is shared on social media platforms.

Another concern is that online posting leads to copycat crimes among people who consume the content. Exposure to aggression or crime news, especially children, affects socialization and decision-making (Brainard. 2018). The sharing of mass killings, terrorism, heists, murder, and other violent content increases pessimism among the public while increasing the chances of the audience engaging in criminal activities.

Individuals and criminal gangs' propaganda spread on social media significantly impacts social media users. For instance, reports of successful attacks and raids by terrorists motivate the audience to join the movements knowing that they can succeed in committing the attacks. This influence is a big concern since it jeopardizes public safety and peace. Hence, displaying crimes on social media is problematic due to the risk of general chaos and anarchy.

3.7 Outcomes: Influence on deviant behavior in the future, what worked in regulating Twitter & Instagram's influence, and what did not

In ten years, Twitter and Instagram will increasingly influence people's views on crimes and offenders. The users receive real-time news about crimes and related activities from the two platforms. In the past, individuals relied on traditional forms of communication, such as television and newspapers. Today, news feeds, and trending subjects are rising on Twitter and Instagram, a trend poised to increase in the future as more people have access to the internet. Therefore, the rates and complexity of crime will increase as more users join and rely on Twitter and Instagram as sources related to crime.

Similarly, Twitter and Instagram will continue to encourage performance-related crime because of the increasing celebrity culture. In the next ten years, musicians and other famous

people will continue to post illegal activities regarding gangs and drugs, including money laundering, armed robberies, and violence, commonly associated with the industry. The celebrity culture will push many people to post pre-crime confessions, clips of them committing crimes, and footage after they are done. Criminal justice officers can use the videos as evidence.

Based on the trends in the past ten years, the lack of regulation of both platforms will lead to misuse and misinformation, resulting in lawlessness and crime proliferation. The sites have consistently been used for radical social and political mobilizations on emotive matters, such as racism, anti-immigrant, anti-refugee, terrorism, violence, and crime (Wahlström & Tömberg, 2021). Consequently, the inability of society to implement a clear law on content generated and shared on these platforms will mobilize and coordinate online extremism and criminal activities.

For instance, forum discussions on Twitter and Instagram provide an avenue of producing sentiments and narratives that legalize political violence or normalize bullying and racism. Exposure to extremist content would influence an individual's propensity to act violently. People would also learn how offenders commit some crimes while evading consequences. Incidences of incitement and hatemongering would become more prevalent because online content creation and sharing are censored. Some people, including leaders and influencers, do not use social media responsibly as they spread hate speech and violence to other users.

Fake news is another challenge for non-regulated social media accounts. Many accounts are anonymous, implying that their public details cannot be verified. The anonymity lends to a lack of accountability as the consumers cannot authenticate the shared information. If a legal framework were not developed to control the criminal attitudes on Twitter and Instagram, the situation would be exacerbated as perpetrators of violence and hate would remain unpunished.

The statutory building code that requires social media platforms to have mandatory quality and safety requirements for their users has regulated authority over the media. Still, the artificial intelligence (AI) law failed. Companies should examine the potential harms and have the engineers design platforms that do not jeopardize users' safety and character. Additionally, political leaders play a critical role in determining the effectiveness of the enacted regulatory policies based on their self-interests (Helberger, 2020).

The regulatory strategies mentioned above have controlled the power and authority of Twitter and Instagram. However, a legal requirement for organizations to design their systems with artificial intelligence (AI) technologies to detect and filter violent content has failed. The law's stakeholders and regulatory nature hinder the legislation's efforts to embed the existing legal framework (Macdonald et al., 2019). Maintenance of the public-private distinction is complex, restricting the efficient implementation of the AI regulation.

Social media's influence on violent behavior and crime is concerning. It was possible to avoid using social media about a decade ago, when users had the option to quickly disappear from the web and carry on with their daily activities. This solution is no longer viable as most businesses, institutions, and social groups rely on social media to communicate and get news or updates. A significant reason online crimes have become such a menace is the government's slow pace at keeping up with technology or regulating the platform (Yar, 2018). The emotional and psychological consequences of cyber victimization are known. However, the criminal justice system has hardly invested in the resources required to regulate activity on social media.

It is important to note that cyberbullying and online victimization lack adequate criminal codes to guide the justice system (Ajayi, 2016). As such, courts rely on outdated standards for

processing charges linked to crimes such as online fraud, hacking, extortion, and intimidation. The legislature, law enforcement, and the justice system need to recruit new talents from social media platforms. Relying on platforms to ensure the public's safety should never be considered an option simply because of its ineffectiveness.

Twitter and Instagram's methods in regulating violent posts from reaching millions, perhaps billions, are inefficient because it is up to the user to choose whether the post they see is violent or not. Methods such as the 'report post' option and warning signs appearing before violent posts proved how these platforms are invested in the usage of their platforms more than their users' safety, allowing them to view violent posts regardless of the warning signs they attach. A derivative organization that has no benefit in social media businesses is required to interfere with banning the spread of successful and planned attacks.

CHAPTER 4: CONCLUSION

Peer effect, lack of appropriate regulation, anonymity, and freedom of expression make crime content and misinformation spread faster on these platforms than any other mainstream channel. Social media is a powerful tool that can be constructive or destructive, depending on its use. Responsible use of Twitter and Instagram is key to combating crime perpetration and misinformation. A proactive and multi-tasked approach needs to be adopted to combat the harmful use of social media. Government agencies need to cope with technological advancements despite social media's benefits. Cybercriminals have used the platforms to benefit themselves and abused the purpose of these platforms.

As to the users, or targets, their privacy and safety remain unsecured. Coping mechanisms such as the implementation of AI and government agencies' interference are necessary to combat crime perpetration. Relying solely on social media officials is an ineffective safety mechanism due to the rise in criminal activities and violent posts on social media. A derivative organization or governmental organization must prove its disinterest in social media platforms, then establish authority over these platforms.

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